

PROTOCOL

**H2O-F – A PROSPECTIVE, MULTI-COUNTRY,
MULTI-CENTRE, MULTI-CONDITION FEASIBILITY
STUDY EVALUATING THE ESTABLISHMENT OF
THE NATIONAL HEALTH OUTCOMES
OBSERVATORY (H2O) ECOSYSTEM**

**STUDY
INITIATOR:** Health Outcomes Observatory

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KEY MESSAGES

Key Messages

- What is already known on this topic – Patient-reported outcomes offer new insights into patient wellbeing, however, the best means for implementation across multiple countries and collection sites has not been assessed.
- What this study adds – The user preferences of patients and healthcare providers for the inputting and viewing of patient-reported outcomes will be identified and applied.
- How this study might affect research, practice or policy – Results of this study will offer insights into the best practices for the collection and combination of patient-reported and clinically-reported outcomes, as well as for the organization and presentation of health data for multiple stakeholders.

ABSTRACT

The Health Outcomes Observatory project (H2O) is a public-private joint initiative aimed at the standardization and collection of patient-reported outcomes (PROs) and their (real-time) integration with clinical outcomes/measures at a large, international scale. In doing so, our mission is to help facilitate treatment decision-making, empower the patient's voice and improve self-management, as well as to support a broad spectrum of healthcare research. A significant barrier to the wide-scale collection and utilization of PROs concerns the implementation of new technology. In order to ensure that both the patient-facing and healthcare provider-facing dashboards/interfaces are user friendly for both stakeholders a feasibility study must be conducted. To begin, four chronic disease areas will be included in four initial countries. The flow of patient data will be tested for fidelity along the newly developed technology structure for each disease area, and the data collection system and data retrieval system - including their associated interfaces – will be assessed for their user experiences and usability. An assessment of the perceived clinical utility for both the patient and the healthcare professional is also conducted to begin evaluating the change this represents in terms of medical care. In addition, a maturity model has been internally developed by the project for the purpose of assessing the progress of each participating national observatory development at the time of the study. In summation, the primary goals the study are 1) testing the data journey, 2) testing the user experience and usability of the H2O system, 3) collect preliminary evidence of the data's value, and 4) assess the overall progress of the observatories. The findings from this study will help ensure that health data from multiple sources and disease areas can be collected and utilized efficiently, which is crucial for its usefulness in personalized treatments, population health, regulation, and more.

FEASIBILITY STUDY PROTOCOL

BACKGROUND

Healthcare systems globally are not performing optimally. Healthcare costs are growing rapidly, and fragmentation and duplication of care result in waste of resources (2). With aging populations and the growing burden of non-communicable and chronic diseases, healthcare systems are facing huge sustainability challenges. Moreover, healthcare systems lack the ability to measure and improve system performance while providing transparency on health outcome data.

The concept of 'value' in health has emerged in the discourse surrounding healthcare transformation in recent decades (3). Value has been defined as improving health outcomes in relation to the costs required to achieve them (4). Value-based care postulates that patient's outcomes and their care experiences can be improved through the systematic capture and appraisal of their perspectives. In recent years, healthcare systems have started examining the value-based healthcare concept and applying some of the academic foundations (5). However, health outcome data, costs and, in particular, patients' perspectives, are not routinely collected as standard practice across all

conditions and care pathways in the context of care delivery. In order to improve the health and wellbeing of populations, healthcare systems must evaluate performance using metrics that are person-centred and relevant to the citizens they serve (6).

Over previous decades, scientific advances in the understanding of disease biology, innovation, and the emergence of new health technologies and treatments have tremendously increased survival for many medical conditions. However, it is also crucial to evaluate the impact that care and therapeutic interventions have on health-related quality of life beyond mortality. This requires capture and incorporation of patient-generated outcome data with clinical data.

Patient-reported outcomes (PROs) are any report of the status of a patient's health condition that comes directly from the patient, without interpretation of the patient's response by a clinician or anyone else (7). One way to measure these aspects of health is using validated patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) which are completed directly by patients to assess the effects of symptoms, treatment, or both on a patient's functional status (e.g., symptom burden, effects, psychological well-being and social functioning) (8) and health-related quality of life (9). Through measurement of outcomes from the patients' perspective, PRO data can influence the decision-making of multiple healthcare system stakeholders, improve care pathways and health policies, inform health technology assessment, augment medicines development and regulatory approval, and support more effective communication between patients and healthcare professionals (10, 11).

The most significant perceived benefits of PROs are the ability to track changes in symptoms over time, better control the disease and improve quality of care. In fact, there is evidence that monitoring of self-reported symptoms and timely reaction of the healthcare teams can result in adjustment to patients' treatment (12) and even increase patients' survival (13). For example, the implementation of self-reported symptom monitoring into the clinical management of cancer patients has been shown to lead to clinical benefits, including quality-adjusted survival and lower hospitalisation rates (14, 15).

While PROMs have been widely implemented in clinical trials, research settings, and medicines development (16, 17), their use in routine clinical practice has been limited so far despite the documented benefits. Moreover, PROs are often still collected using pen and paper, potentially leading to errors, such as transcription mistakes (18, 19) (20), as well as delayed accessibility of data due to the manual entry process (18, 21). In addition, PROM data have mostly been collected at aggregate-level for providers' improvement initiatives (22), rather than at the individual patient-level to support care delivery and patient-clinician interaction.

Remote and systematic collection of PROMs can support real-time monitoring of symptoms, detection of changes in disease progression and enable timely intervention (15). PROs must constitute an integral part of an overall health outcome measurement scheme (23-25) and their assessment is most important for driving a patient-centred

approach in healthcare by enabling patient self-management, engagement and eventually empowerment.

To leverage the full potential of health outcome data in routine care delivery and for research it is crucial to integrate clinical data, PROs, and patient characteristics and relevant care process data. Core outcome sets (COS) represent a minimally sufficient set of patient-relevant outcomes for collection in clinical trials or routine care for a particular disease or condition, and can also include case-mix variables, patient characteristics and other administrative or care process data. They are developed through a consensus process involving a range of stakeholder perspectives in order to ensure they are valid and accepted, and this standardisation is important to support decision making (26, 27). The consents, ethics forms, and measures were adapted for local systems and languages while ensuring sufficient standardization for a robust analysis.

STUDY RATIONALE

Despite demonstrated benefits of the incorporation of PROMs into routine clinical practice, this is not yet done at scale across healthcare systems as standard of care. Barriers include the lack of standardisation of different domains and measurement tools, as well as the lack of an infrastructure and best practice models for the efficient and structured collection, storage, processing, and usage of these data longitudinally and in an ethical and sustainable manner. Moreover, lack of trust and transparency around health data sharing is an underlying barrier that must be tackled. Patients as citizens rightly demand that their privacy is safeguarded, their data protected and governed in accordance with the consent they exercise (28).

Health Outcomes Observatory (H2O) is a public-private partnership funded by the Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI) and European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations (EFPIA) which will enable patient-centred, ethically and legally sound, data-driven, and outcome focused, healthcare systems in Europe. It is a catalytic project that will architect a multinational ecosystem to incorporate patient-reported and other health outcome data into healthcare decision-making across Europe (29). The H2O consortium is comprised of five countries each with an associated national observatory: Austria, Netherlands, Germany, Spain, and Denmark. All but the latter will participate in the feasibility study. For the purposes of this study, people with diabetes, breast and lung cancer, and irritable bowel disease patients will be included.

The national Health Outcomes Observatory ecosystems will incorporate the patient perspective into healthcare decision making by systematically collecting, storing, and processing health outcomes data so it is easily accessible by the patient, for review in routine clinical practice, and accessible for secondary research and analysis. This will be achieved through establishing national health outcome observatories as non-for-profit entities initially in four countries (Austria, Germany, the Netherlands, Spain), and collecting

health data across three diseases: diabetes, breast and lung cancer, and inflammatory bowel disease.

The four national observatories will be underpinned by a legal and ethical governance model that facilitates data sharing and its use as a natural resource to foster innovation in care delivery and research in the interest of patients, science, and society. The national observatories will operate under a governance model that will guarantee that data are protected under jurisdictional data protection laws. Special attention will be paid to the protection of privacy, personal data, and general data protection.

The activities to establish the national observatories are separate to this study and not described here in detail. This feasibility study will assess the maturity of the implementation of the national Health Outcomes Observatory ecosystems on core metrics (see Figure 1).

BENEFIT/RISK ASSESSMENT

No additional risks are anticipated through participation in the study than those that would be expected from daily life. Potential benefits include societal contribution to healthcare and science, personal enrichment of the participants' treatment course and understanding of their wellbeing.

STUDY OBJECTIVES

The primary objective of this study is to assess the progress of the national H2O Health Outcomes Observatory ecosystem towards a fully functional and operational state using the Maturity Model depicted in Figure 1.

The secondary objectives are to

- Measure the national Health Outcomes Observatory ecosystem's usability and utility for routine care delivery and secondary research health data use cases,
- Understand stakeholders' acceptance, identify facilitators and improve and deepen the situational, contextual qualitative understanding of the perceived barriers and challenges that could prevent implementation and scalability, and
- Evaluate the infrastructure established to capture, store, and analyse integrated clinical and patient-generated health outcome data.

	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4
	Initial	Basic	Progressing	Advancing
Outcome set collection/number of patients	H2O COS* collected; >20 patients per disease (incl. min. 1 follow-up)	>100 patients per country	>500 patients per country	>1000 patients per country
Primary data use for patients	Access to own PRO results (including longitudinal data)	+ averages from other patients	+ clinical data which are relevant	+ averages from clinical data from other patients
Primary data use for HCPs (clinical use)	PRO results available to HCPs	+ averages from other patients	+ integration in EHR	+ averages from clinical data from other patients
Secondary data use – data sharing for researchers	Access to COS* (PRO & clinical) data to researchers from the H2O consortium on site	Access to COS (PRO & clinical) data to researchers from the H2O consortium	+ researchers outside the H2O consortium	Same as level 3
Patient consent	H2O Consent**	H2O Consent	H2O Consent	H2O Consent
Diseases covered	IBD, Breast/Lung Cancer and/or Diabetes (minimum of 1)	Same as level 1	IBD, Breast/Lung Cancer and/or Diabetes (more than 1)	Min. one additional disease covered
Number of patient-facing technology partners	1 per country	2 per country	3 per country	4+ per country
Number of and type of additional sites	0	1-2 per country, including 1 outpatient/primary care	3-4 sites per country, including 1 outpatient/primary care	4+ per country, including 2+ outpatient/primary care
Independent patient utilisation	Possible	Possible	Implemented	Implemented
Patient portability	Possible	Possible	Implemented	Implemented
Linkability to existing data sources	-	Possible	Possible	Implemented

*COS = Core Outcome Set, includes PRO and clinical data; **adjusted nationally to local legal and ethical requirements

Figure 1 H2O Maturity Model

In the context of this protocol, stakeholders include patients, HCPs, healthcare administrators, healthcare policy makers, and academic and private sector researchers.

STUDY DESIGN

A prospective multi-centre, multi-country, multi-condition non-interventional feasibility study with a mixed methods approach will be conducted. Multiple sites in each country will participate. Note that the collection of COS data is considered non-interventional according to local regulation of [\[Countries insert\]](#).

Digital technology solutions which can be operated via smartphone, tablet or web-browser will be used to capture PROs and display data. Data architecture will be implemented in accordance with the plans for the national Health Outcomes Observatory ecosystems and the local privacy and cybersecurity standards. Participation in this study is not intended to change the routine clinical care that patients receive; all treatment decisions and type and timing of disease monitoring are at the discretion of the treating physician. No additional visits to the clinic will be required for the purposes of the study.

Start of study

The study start date will be the date of the first patient consenting to participate. The planned start date is [\[Q1 2023\]](#).

End of study

The end of the study will be the date from which the last information of the last subject included in the feasibility study is recorded in the study database. The planned end of study date is [Q2/3 2024].

Length of study

This study will last [18 months], including a recruitment period of [6 months]. Data of each participant will be collected over a period of 12 months.

Trained site personnel will obtain informed consent and enrol patients meeting the eligibility criteria. Clinical and PRO data will be collected for a period of 12 months after enrolment (end-of-study assessment) in the context of the feasibility study. Enrolled patients will be provided access to and trained on the use of the digital tools, e.g., PRO device to complete baseline and interval-based assessments. Patient data will be collected, but no remote monitoring system will be established.

Study population

All patients with a diagnosis of Metastatic Breast Cancer, Lung Cancer, Crohn's Disease, Ulcerative Colitis or Type I and Type II Diabetes who are treated at participating centres and other H2O stakeholders such as HCPs, healthcare administrators, healthcare policy makers, and academic and private sector researchers.

3.5.1 Rationale for Study Design

This feasibility study does not impose a therapy protocol, diagnostic/therapeutic procedure, or a visit schedule. Patients will be enrolled into the study during a routine clinical visit. Baseline demographic variables will be extracted from existing clinical databases or by asking the patients.

The feasibility testing will be consistent with guidance proposed by Eldridge et al. (30) and Sluggett et al. (31). A mixed methods approach will be undertaken to assess feasibility. The quantitative measurements will be used to construct a semi-structured interview with a sub-sample of participants. Using this qualitative approach, the researchers can focus and addresses problem areas indicated in the questionnaires.

PATIENT TARGET POPULATION

All patients will be required to have a diagnosis of either Type I or Type II Diabetes, Crohn's Disease, Ulcerative Colitis, Metastatic Breast Cancer, or Lung Cancer diagnosed according to standard criteria at the time of study entry. Patients who meet the eligibility criteria will be invited to participate in the study. Eligibility will be assessed prior to enrolment during a routine visit.

Subjects must meet the following inclusion criteria for study entry:

Patients (>18 years of age) with a diagnosis of Type I or Type II Diabetes, Crohn's Disease, Ulcerative Colitis, Metastatic Breast Cancer, or Lung Cancer.

Ability to read and understand [\[insert local language\]](#).

Evidence of a signed and dated H2O patient agreement (written or in electronic format), as per local requirements, which clearly indicates that the patient has been informed of all pertinent aspects to participate in the national Health Outcomes Observatory ecosystem.

Signed and dated informed consent form for participation in the feasibility study or electronic record indicating that the patient has been informed of all pertinent aspects of the study and consented to participation in the study.

Willing and able to complete data collection using an electronic device.

Subjects who meet any of the following criteria will be excluded from study entry:

Any patient who is unable or unwilling to provide explicit informed consent, or fails to meet other inclusion criteria.

Note that patients who are diagnosed with more than one condition in the scope of the H2O feasibility study can only be recruited once (on the basis of one of the conditions only). Patient eligibility must be reviewed, confirmed, and documented by an appropriately qualified member of the study team prior to study enrolment.

3.6.1 RATIONALE FOR SUBJECT POPULATION

The initial disease areas, diabetes (Type I and Type II), inflammatory bowel disease (Crohn's Disease and Ulcerative Colitis) and cancer (Lung Cancer and Metastatic Breast Cancer) have been chosen to demonstrate proof-of-concept and utility of the health data ecosystem. These disease areas were selected based on disease burden, and their span of acute and chronic conditions, recognition of the value of PRO data and patient-centred care, and progress towards digitalisation of care. For this study, we will recruit all willing participants diagnosed with these conditions and treated at participating centres.

NUMBER OF SUBJECTS PARTICIPATING IN THE STUDY

We intend to include a total of 200 patients (a minimum of 50 at each site) with of Type I or Type II Diabetes, Crohn's Disease, Ulcerative Colitis, Metastatic Breast Cancer, or Lung Cancer in this study. 25 patients in one site should have one disease. Type I and II would classify as one disease. In addition, 6 patients per disease and 3 HCPs working in the respective disease areas, stratified for age and gender, will be asked to complete a semi-structured qualitative interview between 9 and 12 months from the start of their participation in the feasibility study. In addition, stakeholders such as healthcare administrators, healthcare policy makers, and academic and private sector researchers could also be included in the qualitative part of the H2O-F study.

This study is designed to provide descriptive, qualitative information and not for hypothesis testing. As such, no formal power calculation has been performed to determine sample size. Instead, the recruitment target was established on a practical basis in conjunction with estimated ability to have reasonable precision around key estimates.

PARTICIPATING SITES

At least 4 hospitals will participate in the study in 4 countries. The following hospitals have already agreed to participate: [\[insert hospitals\]](#). Additional countries and centres may be added in due course.

RECRUITMENT PROCEDURE

Recruitment into the feasibility study will be performed by HCPs or other clinical staff at participating centres during a routine visit. Informational and onboarding materials for both patients and HCPs will be available to support this process. Patients who are interested in participating in the feasibility study will be asked to sign a written or electronic informed consent prior to participation. Once informed consent has been obtained, the HCP, with possible support from technology providers, will provide the patients with onboarding and access instructions for using the application and for filling out the questionnaires. Stratified for age, gender and educational status (purposive sampling), a subset of the participants will be asked whether they would be interested to also participate in a semi-structured interview carried out as part of the feasibility testing. Patients will be able to withdraw from the study at any time without providing a reason.

VARIABLES

Variables will consist of disease-specific COS data (PROs, clinical outcomes, and patient characteristics), maturity model metrics, clinical and demographic variables extracted from electronic medical records, satisfaction and utility questionnaires, and experiences captured through qualitative interviews.

Primary variable

The primary variable of this study is as follows:

National observatory implementation assessed according to the maturity model metrics after 6, 9, and 12 months. The implementation level will be scored according to the achievement of the minimum metrics on all parameters. The parameters are detailed in the maturity model in **Figure 1**.

Secondary variables

Secondary variables will be collected from patients, healthcare professionals (HCPs), healthcare administrators, healthcare policy makers, and academic and private sector researchers using qualitative (i.e., semi-structured interviews) and quantitative (i.e., questionnaires) tools:

- Patients' acceptance and perceived clinical utility of the national Health Outcomes Observatory ecosystem (qualitative assessment on a subset of patients).
- HCPs' acceptance and perceived clinical utility of the national Health Outcomes Observatory ecosystem (qualitative assessment on a subset of participants).
- Healthcare policy makers' and academic and private sector researchers' perceived secondary of the national Health Outcomes Observatory ecosystem (qualitative assessment).
- Patient satisfaction with care as measured by the Short-Form Patient Satisfaction Questionnaire (PSQ-18) at baseline, month 6 and month 12.
- Patient perceived clinical utility of national Health Outcomes Observatory ecosystem as measured by the Patient Utility Questionnaire at months 6 and 12.
- Patient perceived usability of digital solutions as measured by the System Usability Scale (SUS) at month 6.
- HCPs perceived clinical utility of the national Health Outcomes Observatory ecosystem as measured by the HCP Utility questionnaire at months 6 and 12.
- HCPs perceived usability of digital solutions as measured by the System Usability Scale (SUS) at month 6.
- Researcher perceived utility of data collected under the H2O framework as measured by the [\[Research Utility questionnaire\]](#) at months 6 and 12.

Other variables of interest are:

Patient adoption calculated as the proportion of invited patients who accepted the invitation and registered.

Patient adherence calculated as the average proportion of patients who completed the data collection according to the schedule in the first [\[3/6 months\]](#).

Reason for stopping national observatory participation (if possible).

Reason for declining to participate (if possible).

Completeness of transferred data and occurrence of technical issues.

Likelihood of recommendation of national observatory according to net promoter score.

Assessment of setting for and device used for patient data collection according to questionnaire.

DATA SOURCES

Participants' and study data will be recorded in the study database. Study data will be collected at defined time points (see Section 1.5) using different sources:

- Maturity model survey.

- Electronic medical records for the collection of patient medical information.
- Disease-specific PRO measures using digital technology solutions.
- Patient-reported satisfaction, perceived clinical utility and usability questionnaires.
- Clinician-reported perceived clinical utility and usability questionnaires.
- Researcher-reported perceived utility questionnaire.
- Semi-structured interview recordings and transcripts.

Additional qualitative and quantitative data will be collected to assess feasibility, namely, interface usability concerning PROM entry, patient experiences, and process assessment indicators.

The degree of detail and completeness of data collected is dependent on local clinical practice. However, every effort should be taken by the study sites to minimise missing data.

In this feasibility study, information collected using PRO questionnaires on digital technology solutions will be directly transferred into the database, and there will be no secondary data sources. In addition, data from electronic medical records and [\[national registries\]](#) will be used, and the PRO measures will be scored according to relative instrument's scoring algorithm.

DATA COLLECTION

In the routine care setting, subjects are seen regularly by their treating physicians, either for treatment or for regular follow-up. Thus, no additional study-specific visits to the clinical centres are required by this protocol. PRO measures and other questionnaires will be collected using digital technology solutions that enable remote data collection. Reminder functionalities will be used to minimise missing data.

All patients, across all disease areas, will complete a patient satisfaction questionnaire (Patient Satisfaction Questionnaire Short-form (PSQ-18)) at baseline, month 6 and month 12 from enrolment, and a Patient-perceived Clinical utility questionnaire at months 6 and 12 from enrolment. All clinicians will complete a Perceived Clinical utility questionnaire at 6 and 12 months from the start of the study. Researchers will complete a perceived Research utility questionnaire at 6 and 12 months from the start of the study. Patients and clinicians will complete a quantitative assessment of digital solution interface usability using the System Usability Scale (SUS) (32) at 6 months from the start of the study. The assessment schedule involving the administration of these tools is reported in **Table 1** (see synopsis).

In addition, a subset of 6 patients and 3 healthcare professionals in each disease area, stratified for age and gender, will be invited to complete a short semi-structured qualitative interview between 9 and 12 months from the start of participation in the feasibility study.

Patients with no evidence of cognitive impairment will be recruited into the qualitative study by HCPs. The interview guide will be built upon the insight gathered through the above-listed quantitative questionnaires, allowing for an increased degree of focused exploration and reducing the anticipated number of required participants. Hence, patients interviewed must have first completed the above questionnaires. These will inform and shape the semi-structured interviews. A starting list of open-ended questions can be found in **Appendix 5**. HCPs and patients will be contacted by phone or email to schedule an online interview. The interviews will be recorded and transcribed for analysis.

Finally, patients will be administered disease-specific PRO measures at least every 3 months and in accordance with the disease-specific Delphi studies (see **Table 1**, synopsis). Frequency of data collection may increase where allowed by digital solutions and if agreed with patients. Disease-specific core outcome sets are reported in **Appendix 2**.

3.12.1 DATA COLLECTED AT FEASIBILITY STUDY COMPLETION

At study completion, participating patients and healthcare professionals will be invited to provide feedback on their experience using an open field response option survey questionnaire.

The Patient Satisfaction Questionnaire Short-form (PSQ-18), maturity model parameters, patient and healthcare professional perceived utility, and researcher utility will be collected at study completion.

SUBJECT, STUDY, AND SITE DISCONTINUATION

3.13.1 SUBJECT WITHDRAWAL

Subjects have the right to withdraw their consent to data storage and collection at any time and without providing a reason. Expected reasons for withdrawal from the study may include, but are not limited to:

Consent withdrawal

Loss to follow-up

Death.

Where possible, the primary reason for withdrawal from the study should be documented. Subjects will not be followed up for any reason after consent has been withdrawn. Subjects who withdraw from the study will not be replaced with exceptions to the qualitative interviews due to the small sample size.

3.13.2 STUDY AND SITE DISCONTINUATION

The study initiator has the right to terminate a site at any time. Reasons for terminating the study may include, but are not limited to:

Subject enrolment is unsatisfactory

{Other reasons}

The study initiator will notify the physician if the study is placed on hold, or if the study initiator decides to discontinue the study. The study initiator has the right to replace a site at any time. Reasons for replacing a site may include, but are not limited to:

Poor protocol adherence

Inaccurate or incomplete data recording.

It is important to note that discontinuation from the feasibility study does not imply automatic exclusion from the H2O overall.

DATA MANAGEMENT

Patient-reported data will be captured using the digital solution designed, programmed, and hosted by [insert name]. These data will be transferred to [insert name] for analysis as part of the study's primary objectives. Data transfers between [insert name] will be managed using procedures described in a jointly developed Data Transfer Plan. All data transferred between [insert name] will be identified only by a subject ID code, unless otherwise consented by patients and agreed upon in the Data Transfer Plan. Data in both systems will be compared regularly to ensure that participant status is the same in both systems. [insert name] will combine the database at the end of the study.

3.14.1 DATA QUALITY ASSURANCE

The participating centres will transfer pseudonymised patient data to the Medical University of Vienna (MUW) for analysis. Only data directly related to the feasibility study will be gathered (e.g., no PROMs) and provided to the MUW for analysis. A process for safe data transfer will be set up by MUW (secure server, encrypted, password protected). Patients will consent that pseudonymised patient data will be transferred and analysed at the MUW. MUW will not share the data with any third parties or collaborators. MUW regularly processes medical data and is subject to the GDPR requirements. MUW is responsible for data quality and will perform oversight of the data management of this study. Investigators and study coordinators will receive an initial training session on the protocol, study flow, study database, mobile applications from PRO capture, documentation, site responsibilities and expectations, and any applicable study processes. Any new information relevant to the performance of this feasibility study will be forwarded to the medical staff during the study. No on-site monitoring visits are planned for this study. Access to data for secondary use cases will be enabled.

3.14.2 SOURCE DATA DOCUMENTATION

Source documents (paper or electronic) are those in which participant data are recorded and documented for the first time. The source documentation for this study will be:

- Participant demographic information and eligibility assessment
- Signed Informed Consent Forms
- Semi-structured interview recordings.

STATISTICAL ANALYSES

The analysis of the feasibility study will be led by MUW in close collaboration with the local principal investigators and researchers of the participating centres. The primary variable is the Maturity Model. Assessment of whether the criteria of the maturity model are fulfilled and at which level will be done by the country teams; one country team will assess another country. Definitions and operationalisation of the criteria will be provided.

In order to ensure the ease of use for patient's participation, a usability analysis will be conducted. The resulting input will be used to guide adjustment of digital solutions. User considerations include the following: time to completion, completeness of questionnaire, frequency of collection, error counts, and satisfaction. Additionally, to ensure the value of the H2O registry the path of the data must be tested and validated. Firstly, the data journey from patient input, to storage, to retrieval, to presentation, must result in no data loss and complete accuracy in transfer. Secondly, the merge ability and interoperability of multiple datasets will be confirmed. In summation, the assessment must show now or feasibly in the future no data loss, complete accuracy in transfer, and readiness at the time of subsequent clinical encounter between patient and health care practitioner. Thus, an overall feasibility analysis will be conducted. Previously developed use cases will be used with real-world data to test the functionalities and practical application of the registry. Descriptive statistics (M, SD, Range, etc.) from data collected on the patient experience (PSQ-18) and the usability (SUS) measures will be used for comparative purposes across centres. Findings from the SUS will be used to approximate the system usability and indicated problem areas will be informed from the qualitative interviews. Subscales of the SUS will be scored and compared to the recommended cut-offs for a satisfactory interface. A pre-post repeated-measure within-subject ANOVA will be conducted to assess the implicit effects of completing PROMs in the healthcare environment on patient experiences. Emphasis for analysis will be placed on the following PSQ-18 subscales: technical quality, time spent with doctor, accessibility and convenience, and communication.

Interview data will be transcribed verbatim using Amberscript (<https://www.amberscript.com/de/>), checked for accuracy and translated to English. We will then conduct a qualitative meaning condensation analysis (33) in close collaboration with the local investigators. We will first divide the participants' answers into parts of text which share a common meaning. We will then assign a code to each unit that best represents their meaning and group these codes under higher-level topics. This manual

qualitative analysis will be supported by computational methods, such as the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) (34). LDA is an unsupervised probabilistic topic modelling technique that extracts the meanings of a pre-defined number of topics and themes. Topics from both manual and computational analyses will be compared and results will be used to refine the topics and consolidate the results. Barriers and facilitators to implement the national H2O ecosystems will be specifically addressed as well as country similarities and differences. Qualitative insights will be discussed in the consortium and will guide the improvement of the H2O model overall.

3.15.1 INTERIM AND FINAL ANALYSES AND TIMING OF ANALYSES

The following analyses for the study are planned:

- Assessment of the maturity model will be done at month 6, 9, and 12 months.
- Analysis at 6 months for patient and HCPs usability.
- Analysis of patient satisfaction at baseline and 6 and 12 months.
- Analysis of HCPs and patient perceived utility at 6 and 12 months.
- Analysis of patient adoption at the end of the recruitment period.
- Analysis of patient adherence at 3 and 6 months.
- Analysis of qualitative interviews will be performed between 9 and 12 months.
- Final analysis at end of the study (all participants will be followed up for [\[insert follow-up period\]](#)).

STUDY DOCUMENTATION AND MONITORING

The physician must maintain adequate and accurate records to enable the conduct of the study to be fully documented, including but not limited to the protocol, protocol amendments, Informed Consent Forms, and documentation of IRB/EC and governmental [{approval/notification}](#). The study initiator shall ensure that the dataset and statistical programs used for generating the data included in the final study report are kept in electronic format and are available for auditing and inspection.

3.16.1 RETENTION OF RECORDS

Archiving at the study site must last for a minimum of five years after final study report or first publication of study results, whichever comes later; or according to local regulation. Records and documents pertaining to the conduct of this study must be retained by the study initiator for at least 25 years after completion of the study, or for the length of time required by relevant national or local health authorities, whichever is longer. After that period of time, the documents may be destroyed, subject to local regulations.

No records may be disposed of without the written approval of the study initiator. Written notification should be provided to the study initiator prior to transferring any records to

another party or moving them to another location. All supporting functional parties will comply with the study initiator procedures regarding archiving and record management.

STUDY LIMITATIONS

The patient selection and the diagnostic or monitoring procedures are those applied per the usual treatment paradigm of the treating physician and not dictated by the protocol. Heterogeneous patient populations could make the interpretation of the outcomes difficult. However, there this study does not aim to investigate the impact of the participation in the Health Outcomes Observatory on patient outcomes. As with all studies that require patients to self-report outcomes and behaviour, completeness and accuracy of reporting can be a concern. The data collection methods have been designed to be appropriate and accessible to the study population. Nevertheless, some errors in recording information and some missing information can be anticipated, particularly given the frequency and length of questionnaires required for data collection. As this study will collect PRO data through the use of devices, ability to use these devices is required and this may limit representativeness of the study sample. In summary, the design of this protocol presents inherent limitations that cannot be prevented and that are typical of non-interventional real-world studies. These studies have the potential for missing, inaccurate, or incomplete data. These limitations can result in methodological challenges in attributing causality to outcomes.

PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS

3.18.1 COMPLIANCE WITH LAWS AND REGULATIONS

This study will be conducted in full conformance with the [\[insert relevant guidelines\]](#) and the laws and regulations of the country in which the research is conducted. Data will be stored and handled according to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Patients will be made aware of their rights to consult or change their own data and of their possibilities to report any faults to the corresponding authorities.

3.18.2 INFORMED CONSENT

The sample Informed Consent Form will be provided to each site by the study initiator. The Consent Forms must be signed and dated before start of documentation entering any data in the study database. The case history or clinical records for each subject shall document the informed consent process and that informed consent was obtained prior to first documentation of this subject's data in the study database. By signing the consent form, subjects confirm that they have been informed about the study procedures and agree to data collection, pooling of data with similar scientific data (if applicable), and the possibility of monitoring activities. It is the responsibility of the physician to ascertain that the subject has understood the study information and to obtain informed consent from each subject participating in the study, after adequate explanation of the aims, methods, anticipated benefits, and potential hazards of the study. The physician must also inform

the subjects of their right to refuse to enter the study or to withdraw from it at any time, for any reason and without effect on the routine medical care. A copy of each signed Consent Form must be provided to the subject. All signed and dated Consent Forms must remain in each subject's study file or in the site file and must be available for verification at any time.

INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD OR ETHICS COMMITTEE

The feasibility study protocol, the Informed Consent Forms, and any study-related material must be submitted to the IRB/EC by the [\[national health outcome observatory responsible person\]](#) and reviewed and approved by the IRB/EC before the study is initiated. In addition, any patient recruitment materials must be approved by the IRB/EC.

CONFIDENTIALITY

The study initiator maintains confidentiality standards by coding each subject enrolled in the study through assignment of a unique subject identification number. This means that identifiable data are not included in datasets that are transmitted to any study initiator's location. Subject medical information obtained by this study is confidential and may be disclosed to third parties only as permitted by the Informed Consent Form (or separate authorisation for use and disclosure of personal health information) signed by the subject, unless permitted or required by law.

The study initiator, including affiliates, collaborators and licensees may use study data labelled with the patient ID numbers. Study data may also be shared with independent researchers or government agencies, but only after removal of identifiable information. Patients' study data may be combined with other patient's data and/or linked to other data collected from the patients. Patients' study data may be used to help better understand why people get diseases, how to best prevent, diagnose and treat diseases, and to develop and deliver access to new medicines, medical devices, and healthcare solutions to advance patient care.

MANAGEMENT OF ADVERSE EVENTS

Although adverse event (AE) information is not actively solicited via this protocol, physician/consumers are reminded to report any adverse reactions (for which they suspect a causal role of a medicinal product prescribed as part of routine medical care) or special situations either to the marketing authorisation holder of the suspected product or to the concerned competent authorities via the national spontaneous reporting system.

3.21.1 REPORTING REQUIREMENTS FOR ADVERSE EVENTS ORIGINATING FROM PATIENT REPORTED OUTCOMES

Physician/study personnel are not expected to review the PRO data for potential adverse events. Due to the non-interventional nature of the study and the only collection of routine clinical data, no adverse events are expected. If patients will disclose information in a questionnaire or qualitative interview that shows the need for additional care of other support, e.g., mental health issues, depressive symptoms etc. the respective patient will be referred to appropriate local healthcare services.

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